

EFFECT OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT ON PHASE SEPARATION OF POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL IN HIGHLY NON-IDEAL SOLUTION

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Abstract

In spite of the modicum of laboratory work on two-phase separation (TPS), the mechanism of the process is still far from being fully understood. Two-phase distribution of polyethylene glycol 6000 (PEG6K) in buffer pH 7.4 (ionic strength, 1.2 – 2.0 mol dm⁻³) and polyethylene (glycol) 70000 (PEG70K) in buffer pH 7.4 (ionic strength, 0.2 – 1.2 mol dm⁻³) were determined in the temperature range between 15 and 40°C. Concentration range of PEG6K used was between 150 and 270 g/dm³, and that of PEG70K was between 10 and 50 g/dm³. The phase separation of PEG70K was characterized by liquid-solid phase distribution whose apparent equilibrium constant increases with increasing concentration of PEG70K at fixed ionic strength. That of PEG6K was characterized by liquid-liquid phase separation of which the complexity of the profile of the dependence of logarithm of equilibrium constant of phase separation on concentration of PEG6K reduces with increasing ionic strength and temperature. At low ionic strength and temperature the profile has a maximum at *ca.* 207 g/dm³ and a minimum at *ca.* 240 g/dm³. The natural logarithm of distribution constant of PEG70K increases with increasing concentration of PEG70K, transforming from concave-down profile at low temperature and ionic strength, to concave-up profile at high ionic strength and high temperature. The finding of this work show that PEG6K is more sensitive to change in concentration of electrolyte per unit polymer than PEG70K. Optimum aqueous two phase separation is achievable by raising the concentration of the electrolyte as the concentration of the polymer is raised in solution.

1. Introduction

PEGs are among the most useful synthetic biopolymers due to their solubility in both water and organic solvents. They have found usefulness in solubilizing poorly soluble drugs thereby enhancing their bioavailability (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2008; Bhalani *et al.*, 2022). They are important in protein purification due to their biocompatibility (Li *et al.*, 2024; Makharadze *et al.*, 2025, Gupta *et al.*, 2019). They have found usefulness in pharmaceuticals, materials science, chemical engineering, cosmetics, and biomedicine because of their solubility, and ability to enhance drug delivery (Gaballa *et al.*, 2024; D'souza and Shegokar, 2016; Hoang Thi *et al.*, 2020). Understanding PEGs' solubility behavior allow for optimizing their use in drug delivery applications, enhancing material properties, and improving their efficiency in industrial processes like carbon capture.

In Pharmaceutical applications, conjugating PEG to drugs or proteins (PEGylation) is known to increases their water solubility, extends their circulation time in the body, and reduce immunogenicity, leading to more effective therapies (D'souza and Shegokar, 2016). Insight into how PEG interacts with different solvents and excipients under various conditions is essential for creating various dosage forms like tablets, films, or injectable solutions.

PEG solubility behaviour is critical to their exploration in the creation of new materials with tailored properties and interactions with other polymers and materials. By controlling PEG's solubility, properties of materials like gels, coatings, and nanocomposites in which they are used can be tailored base on needs.

Studies have shown that an important property that influence solubility of biomolecules, including PEG is the activity coefficient (Pons *et al.*, 2025; Padín-González *et al.*, 2022). The activity coefficient reflects the deviation of a solution from ideal behavior, and significantly influences their solubility and other properties in a solution in the presence of a co-solute. Determination of activity coefficient of a biopolymer is crucial for accurate modeling and prediction of their solubility under a non-ideal condition.

In ideal solutions, the activity of a solute is equal to its concentration. However, real solutions often exhibit non-ideal behavior, and the activity (a) of PEG solute may be related to its concentration (C_{PEG}), and the activity coefficient (γ) by,

$$a = \gamma C_{PEG}. \quad (1)$$

Activity coefficient essentially corrects for deviations from ideal behavior caused by factors like solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions. A high activity coefficient ($\gamma > 1$) which suggests unfavourable interaction between solute molecules or between solute and solvent molecules leads to reduction in the solubility (Marcinkowski *et al.*, 2020; Mbatha *et al.*, 2025). On the other hand, decreased activity coefficient ($\gamma < 1$) suggests stronger attractive forces or more favorable interactions, potentially increasing the solubility of the solute (Pavliš *et al.*, 2023). Among the factors which affect the activity coefficients are; ionic strength, presence of other ions, the size and charge of the ions, and the nature of the solvent (Kournopoulos *et al.*, 2022; May and May, 2024). Ionic strength are known to be increased by increasing the salt concentration in the solution containing proteins and macromolecules. They are also known to increase the activity coefficient contribution of ions, thereby decreasing the solubility of proteins and polymers (Spitzer and Poolman, 2009). There are speculations that organic cosolvents too can affect the solubility of a solute by altering the activity coefficients of both the solute and the solvent (Miyako *et al.*, 2010). Addition of salt are known to decrease the solubility of a non-electrolyte leading to a salting-out effect by increasing the activity coefficient of the solution. The effect of temperature on activity coefficients is not straightforward and depends on the specific solution and its ionic strength. In general, studies have shown that activity coefficients can either increase or decrease with increasing. This behavior is influenced by the interactions between ions and solvent molecules. Previous findings (Rockwood, 2015) have shown that the relationship between temperature and activity coefficients can be linked

to the ionic strength of the solution. For example, at higher ionic strengths (e.g., $I > 0.3 \text{ mol. dm}^{-3}$), activity coefficients increasing with temperature (Szyszkiewicz-Warzecha *et al.*, 2023).

Since ionic strength can be kept constant by maintaining fixed concentration of salt, in this study, we kept the salt concentration constant and determined the equilibrium distribution of PEG between the two phases formed at arbitrary concentration of PEG. The aim is to determine the contribution of PEG to the activity coefficient with changing PEG concentration. Effect of ionic strength on this distribution was determined by repeating the experiment using various fixed ionic strength conditions. The apparent phase distribution constant under different temperature conditions was used to estimate how temperature changes affect each of PEG6K and PEG70K in the experiment. It is hoped that the finding from this experiment will provide insight into the differences that may arise between the effects of ionic strength on PEG solubility on one hand and the effect of temperature on PEG solubility on another hand.

Theory of Measurements.

PEG6K Equilibrium

When PEG6K is dissolved in an aqueous solvent containing substantially high concentration of electrolyte (salt) and polymer, an aqueous two-phase system (ATPS) may be formed. The distribution of PEG6K established in equilibrium between the two phases may be described by the PEG-rich (α -phase) and salt-rich (β -phase) as follows,

In Eq. (2) the subscripts “ α ” and “ β ” denotes the different phases in which PEG6K is distributed.

The equilibrium constant of phase distribution of PEG6K may be described by (Eq. 3)

$$K_{D, \text{PEG6K}} = \frac{\text{Concentration of PEG6K in phase } \alpha}{\text{Concentration of PEG6K in phase } \beta} \cong \frac{\text{Volume of liquid in phase } \alpha}{\text{Volume of liquid in phase } \beta} \quad (3)$$

The justification for the use of Eq. (3) for determining the apparent distribution of PEG6K is that the mass of PEG6K in α – *phase* increases with concentration. If the density of PEG6K in each of the phases is constant, at a fixed temperature, the concentration of PEG6K in each phase should be proportional to the volume of PEG6K in the separated the in that phases. In the absence of phase separation, the concentration PEG6K in β –*phase* in relation to the total volume is the solution is maximum whereas, that in α – *phase* is minimum. Assuming PEG6K, (solute 1) and the electrolyte, co-solute 2 are the only solute present at concentration which is sufficiently high to affect the activity of PEG6K in solution. In phase α , the concentration may be expressed in term of its activity and activity coefficients of the constituent solutes as,

$$c_{1(\alpha)} = \frac{a_{1(\alpha)}}{\gamma_{1(\alpha)}\gamma_{2(\alpha)}} \quad (4)$$

Similar expression may be written for the concentration of solute 1 in the phase β . Therefore the apparent equilibrium constant of distribution of PEG6K in the two phases, measured experimentally at constant temperature may be expressed as,

$$K_D = \frac{a_{1(\alpha)}\gamma_{1(\beta)}\gamma_{2(\beta)}}{a_{1(\beta)}\gamma_{1(\alpha)}\gamma_{2(\alpha)}} \quad (5)$$

Where a_1 is the activity of solute 1 and, γ_1 and γ_2 are the activity coefficients of solutes 1 and 2 respectively in the two phases α and β .

If Γ_i ($i = 1$ or 2) is the net effect of the activity coefficient of solute i described by $\frac{\gamma_{i(\alpha)}}{\gamma_{i(\beta)}}$, then the net effect of the contribution of activity coefficient of species 1 and species 2 are Γ_1 and Γ_2 respectively. From Eq. (5) therefore,

$$K_D = \frac{a_{1(\alpha)}}{a_{1(\beta)}} \frac{1}{\Gamma_1\Gamma_2} \quad (6)$$

By definition, the thermodynamic equilibrium constant in the limit of infinite dilution of both solutes is given by,

$$K^o = \frac{a_{1(\alpha)}}{a_{1(\beta)}} \quad (7)$$

Hence, Equation (7) $\frac{a_{1(\alpha)}}{a_{1(\beta)}}$ may be substituted in equation (6) to give,

$$K_D = K^o \frac{1}{\Gamma_1 \Gamma_2} \quad (8)$$

The natural logarithm of which gives,

$$\ln K_D = \ln K^o - \ln \Gamma_1 - \ln \Gamma_2 \quad (9)$$

Under conditions of constant ionic strength and temperature, $\log K^o$ and $\log \Gamma_2$ are constant, therefore, the term $\ln K^o - \ln \Gamma_2$ is a constant and may be expressed as another constant, $\ln K'^o$,

$$\ln K'^o = \ln K^o - \ln \Gamma_2 \quad (10)$$

Hence

$$\ln K_D = \ln K'^o - \ln \Gamma_1 \quad (11)$$

Applying the theory of McMillan and Mayer (McMillan and Mayer, 1945) the activity coefficient of neutral polymers such as protein, dextran T70, Ficoll 70 have been expanded in term of their weight/ volume concentration, (Minton 1983; Fernandez *et al.*, 2019; Fodeke and Minton, 2011; Fodeke, 2019; Fodeke and Minton, 2013, Fodeke, 2024) according to:

$$\ln \gamma_i(w_j) = \sum_j B_{ij} w_j + \sum_j \sum_k B_{ijk} w_i w_k + \dots \quad (12)$$

In Eq. (12) B_{ij} and B_{ijk} are respectively the two, three and higher body coefficients of interaction between molecules i , j and k . When concentration of PEG6K is varied, at fixed temperature, under the conditions of fixed concentration of electrolyte or at infinite dilution of salt, the only species which affect the chemical potential of the solution is PEG6K. Therefore, $i = j = k = 1$. Eq. (12) may therefore be written as:

$$\ln \Gamma_1(w_1) = B_{11} w_1 + B_{111} w_1^2 + \dots \quad (13)$$

Therefore Eq. (11) may be expressed as,

$$\ln K_D = \ln K'^o - B_{11} w_1 - B_{111} w_1^2 \quad (14)$$

PEG70K Equilibrium Distribution

Determination of the apparent distribution of the PEG70K between the solid phase (s) and liquid phase (aq) may be described by:

Concentration of solid phase in solution is inversely proportional to the transmittance at 600 nm. A value of 1 was used as the base line to describe 100% transmittance (when the light at 600 nm is completely transmitted).

The equilibrium distribution of the solid in the two phases can then be determined by using Eq. (16)

$$K_{D, \text{PEG70K}} = \frac{c_{\text{PEG70K}(s)} g/dm^3}{c_{\text{PEG70K}(aq)} g/dm^3} \cong \frac{1 - T_{600}}{T_{600}} \quad (16)$$

Where T_{600} is the transmittance of the solution at 600 nm, under the equilibrium conditions? Transmittance is related to the absorbance by the expression,

$$T_{600} = 10^{-Abs_{600}} \quad (17)$$

Validity of Equation (16) rests on the relationship between turbidity and concentration of solid PEG70.

In Eq. (16) subscript "aq" and "s" designate the aqueous and the solid phases respectively.

Since there are only two solutes that are present in quantity sufficient to affect the solubility of PEG70K in the buffer, we may express the concentration of PEG70K in each phase in terms of the activity coefficient of the species which contribute to its solubility under the conditions of the experiment. In the solid phase the activity of the PEG70K is expressed by,

$$a_{PEG70K(s)} = c_{PEG70K(s)} \gamma_{PEG70K(s)} \gamma_{\pm(s)} \quad (18)$$

The activity in the aqueous phase it is described by,

$$a_{PEG70K(aq)} = c_{PEG70K(aq)} \gamma_{PEG70K(aq)} \gamma_{\pm(aq)} \quad (19)$$

In Eq. (18) $c_{PEG70K(s)}$ is the weight per dm^3 of solid PEG70K in the solution for which the corresponding activity coefficient of undissolved PEG70K and the electrolyte in the solid phase are $\gamma_{PEG70K(s)}$, $\gamma_{\pm(s)}$ respectively.

Therefore the apparent distribution constant of PEG70K in the presence of electrolyte, Eq. (15) may be expressed as,

$$K_{D,PEG70K} = \frac{a_{PEG70K(s)} \cdot \gamma_{PEG70K(aq)} \gamma_{\pm(aq)}}{a_{PEG70K(aq)} \cdot \gamma_{PEG70K(s)} \gamma_{\pm(s)}} \quad (20)$$

Since by definition, the thermodynamic equilibrium constant for the phase distribution in Eq. (15) is given by the ratio of the activity PEG70K in the solid phase to that in the aqueous phase,

$$K^o = \frac{a_{PEG70K(s)}}{a_{PEG70K(aq)}} \quad (21)$$

The apparent equilibrium phase distribution constant may be expressed in term of the thermodynamic equilibrium constant and activity coefficients of the PEG70K and electrolyte,

$$K_D = K^o \frac{\gamma_{PEG70K(aq)} \gamma_{\pm(aq)}}{\gamma_{PEG70K(s)} \gamma_{\pm(s)}} \quad (22)$$

Since solid may not contribute to the activity coefficients affecting the distribution constant of PEG70K in solution Eq. (22), it is assigned activity coefficient value of 1, K_D may therefore be expressed as;

$$K_{D,PEG70K} = K^o \gamma_{PEG70K(aq)} \gamma_{\pm(aq)} \quad (23)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of both sides of Eq. (23),

$$\ln K_{D,PEG70K} = \ln K^o + \log \gamma_{\pm(aq)} + \ln \gamma_{PEG70K(aq)} \quad (24)$$

At constant ionic strength, $\ln \gamma_{\pm(aq)}$ is constant. Therefore an equilibrium distribution (K''^o) at fixed ionic strength may be obtained from the dependence of PEG70K concentration on $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ according to,

$$\ln K_{D,PEG70K} = \ln K''^o + \ln \gamma_{PEG70K}(w_{PEG70K}) \quad (25)$$

Dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ on w_{PEG70K} should give a regression curve whose intercept is $\ln K''^o$ at constant ionic strength.

From the theory of McMillan and Mayer (McMillan and Mayer, 1945),

$$\ln \gamma_{PEG70K} = B_2 w_{PEG70K} + B_3 w_{PEG70K}^2 + \dots \quad (26)$$

Where B_2 and B_3 are two and three body interaction parameter for PEG70K respectively.

Substitution of Eq. (26) into Eq. (25) gives,

$$\ln K_{D,PEG70K} = \ln K''^o + B_2 w_{PEG70K} + B_3 w_{PEG70K}^2 + \dots \quad (27)$$

The distribution constant of PEG70 at infinite dilution of PEG70K under conditions of fixed ionic strength may be determined from the interpolation of the curve of the regression line to zero PEG70K concentration.

Where

$$\ln K''^o = \ln K^o + \ln \gamma_{\pm(aq)} \quad (28)$$

Since the ionic strength are higher under the conditions of the experiment than the region of validity of Debye Huckel theory, the activity coefficient contribution of the electrolyte was modeled using specific ion interaction theory.. Based on this theory, the activity coefficient of a neutral species may be assumed to depend linearly on ionic strength (Sechenov, 1892) according to Eq. (29),

$$\ln \gamma_{\pm(aq)} = k_m I \quad (29)$$

In Eq. (29) k_m is a Sechenov coefficient. Eq. (28) therefore, becomes

$$\log K''^o = \log K^o + k_m I \quad (30)$$

The dependence of equilibrium distribution of PEG70K at infinite dilution of PEG70K on ionic strength should give the thermodynamic equilibrium constant at the temperature under consideration.

2. Materials and Methods

Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (K_2HPO_4), LOT number L111331402 is a product of Lobal Chemie, disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate ($Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$) Lot number 20150316 is a product of JHD chemicals and monopotassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4) is a product made by Sigma Aldrich. Polyethelene glycol 6000 (PEG6K), number average molecular weight 6000, Lot # BCCC 1842 is a product of Sigma Adrich. HI 2209 pH meter was manufactured by Hanna Instruments. Polyethylene glycol 70000 (Lot # N70620932) with nominal molar mass of 70,000 g/mole is a product of Nanjing Forever Pharmacy Co. Graduated 15 ml centrifuge tubes were produced by Celltreat Scientific Products. Temperature conditions of the experiment were controlled using Grant thermostated water bath equipped with CC 60 Cryocool immersion cooler made by Thermoscientific Neslab.

Method

Separate solutions of $0.5 \text{ mole dm}^{-3} KH_2PO_4$ and $0.5 \text{ mole dm}^{-3} Na_2HPO_4$ were mixed in volume to volume ratio 1:4. The ionic strength of the buffer was then adjusted to 2.2 mole dm^{-3} by adding calculated mass of sodium chloride. Specified volume of stock buffer of ionic strength 2.2 mole dm^{-3} was then diluted to the desired ionic strength ($1.2 - 2.0 \text{ mole dm}^{-3}$) by adding appropriate volume of distilled water to the buffer solution. PEG6K of different concentrations were prepared from this solutions by adding 10 cm^3 of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 of specified ionic strength to accurately weighed mass of PEG6K ($1.5 - 3.5 \text{ g}$) in graduated centrifuge tubes and shaken to dissolve the content. The mixture of PEG6K and phosphate buffer pH 7.4 were allowed to equilibrate in a water bath at a given temperature for about 4 hours. The PEG6K solution in the centrifuge tubes were then observed for phase separation and the volume of the salt-rich lower phase and the PEG6-rich upper phase were read off from the graduated centrifuge tubes. The volume of the PEG6K rich upper layer was determined by difference. At a fixed temperature and ionic strength, the values of the apparent equilibrium constant of PEG6K distribution were calculated from Eq. (3) at different ionic strength. The experiment was carried out at temperatures between 15 and 40°C .

Equilibrium distribution of PEG70K

For PEG70K experiment, $10 - 50 \text{ g/dm}^3$ of the solutions were made by dissolving $0.1 - 0.5 \text{ g}$ of PEG70K in 10 cm^3 of buffer solution (ionic strength between 0.6 and 1.2 mol dm^{-3}). Turbidity was determined from the absorbance measurement of the equilibrium mixture at 600 nm using Shimadzu 1800 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer after thorough mixing. The absorbance was converted to the corresponding transmittance reading and the apparent equilibrium constant of each PEG70K components were then calculated using Eq. (16).

3. Result

Effect of Increasing PEG6K concentration at fixed ionic strength

The experimental data points of the dependence of the semi-logarithm of the equilibrium distribution of PEG6K ($\ln K_{D,PEG6K}$) on the g/dm^3 concentration of PEG6K (w_{PEG6K}) at fixed ionic strength were presented in Figure 1. The line through the experimental data points reported in Fig. 1 were fitted with Eq. (14) using parameters reported in Table 1. Panel A describes the experiment at 15°C . Panel B is for experiment at 20°C . Panels C, D, E, and F presents the experiment at 25, 30, 35 and 40°C respectively. It is clear that in the lower ionic strength range, the fit of the curves of Eq. (14) to the experimental data points were poor. The dependence is most complex at the least ionic strength (1.2 mol. dm^{-3}) and least temperature, with a minimum, at *ca.* 240.0 g dm^3 and two maxima,

at *ca.* 206.6 and 257.0 g. dm³. At ionic strength of 1.4 mol. dm⁻³ the profile of the dependence was less complex with a maximum at *ca.* 206.6 g dm³ and a minimum at *ca.* 240.0 g dm³. The complexity of the profile at low ionic strength may be due to non-uniform electrostatic interaction, due to insufficient screening of the PEG6K molecules in the buffer solution. This is especially so as the proportion of electrolyte surrounding each PEG6K molecules becomes smaller with increasing concentration of PEG6K at fixed ionic strength. With increasing ionic strength however, the complex profile of dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG6K}$ at fixed ionic strength transforms into simple profile whose fit with Eq. (14) improves with increasing ionic strength. This is evident from the R² values reported in column 6 of Table 1. Comparing shape of the profiles at different ionic strength for the same temperature, the dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG6K}$ on w_{PEG6K} gets simpler and transforms from a concave-down profile to a concave-up shaped profile. This trends cut across all temperatures conditions of the experiment. The implication of this observation is that at high ratio of ionic strength to concentration of PEG6K, repulsive interaction are screened off thus making attractive interaction which results in phase separation dominant. However as w_{PEG6K} increases at low ionic strength, attractive interaction decreases, as the ratio of ionic strength to PEG6K reduces leading to repulsion between PEG6K molecules. At fixed ionic strength, this repulsion increases with w_{PEG6K} with the consequence that the apparent equilibrium distribution constant decreases. At low strength, with increasing PEG6K concentration, screening becomes less efficient and electrostatic interaction between PEG6K may become important at high concentration which brings the PEG6K molecules closer than its ionic atmosphere.

Figure 1: Dependence of the semi-logarithm of the apparent phase distribution constant of PEG6K on concentration of PEG6K in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at (A) 15°C, (B) 20°C, (C) 25°C, (D) 30°C, (E) 35°C (F) 40°C. Symbols of ionic strength in mol dm⁻³: 1.2, x with grid dotted line; 1.4, + with dotted short line; 1.6, * with short broken line; 1.8, square with long broken line; 2.0, circle with full solid line. Each experimental data point is the mean of at least three replicate experiment subject to 10% standard error.

This suggests that the electrolyte used enhanced phase separation of PEG6K by screening off repulsive interaction between PEG6K molecules, thus enhancing attractive interaction between PEG6K molecules. Increased concentration PEG6K results at fixed ionic strength results in reducing number of electrolyte per molecule of PEG6K hence, with consequent increased repulsion leading to reduced phase separation. In other words, phase separation is sustained when increased concentration of the polymer is matched by increased ionic strength leading to increased or maintained screening of the polymer molecules. Worthy of note is the observation that at high ionic strength, though the PEG6K molecules were screened, attractive contribution to the interaction gets more significant with increasing concentration of PEG6K. This is evident in the value of negative value of the three body interaction coefficient B_{111} . The consequence of this is a negative sloping concave-up profile of the dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG6K}$ on w_{PEG6K} which is typical of dominance of attractive interaction at much higher w_{PEG6K} . At ionic strength 1.6 mol. dm^{-3} , the best-fit line through the experimental data point using Eq. (14) especially at temperature $\geq 25^\circ C$ are essentially a straight line with a negative slope, characteristic of a transition from a dome shaped concave down profile below $25^\circ C$ to a negatively sloping concave-up profile above 1.6 mol. dm^{-3} . The implication of this is that at 1.6 mol. dm^{-3} , the net repulsive interaction decreases linearly with w_{PEG6K} over the concentration range of measurement. This is also evident in the values of the fitting parameters, B_{11} and B_{111} in each case. This transition in the shape of the curve could be used as a proof that increased temperature affect phase separation by reducing or eliminating repulsive interaction between PEG6K molecules.

Table 1. Fitting parameters of the dependence of the natural logarithm of the dependence of apparent distribution constant of PEG6000 at ionic strength between 1.2 and 2.0 mol. dm^{-3} of Figure 1 according to equation (14).

Temp. ($^\circ C$)	I (mol. dm^{-3})	$\ln K'^o$	B_{11} ($dm^3 g^{-1}$)	$B_{111} \times 10^5$ ($dm^6 g^{-2}$)	R^2
15	1.2	-3.665 ± 4.616	-0.0104 ± 0.0444	2.5030 ± 10.4636	0.012
	1.4	-4.564 ± 2.351	-0.0258 ± 0.0227	6.2278 ± 5.3314	0.227
	1.6	0.73316 ± 6.42	0.0151 ± 0.0619	-2.2453 ± 14.55	0.757
	1.8	0.353 ± 0.623	0.0056 ± 0.0060	0.3941 ± 1.4111	0.979
	2	2.857 ± 0.705	0.0266 ± 0.0068	-4.5591 ± 1.5989	0.975
20	1.2	-6.350 ± 2.614	-0.0369 ± 0.0252	8.5663 ± 5.9257	0.322
	1.4	-5.150 ± 2.053	-0.0305 ± 0.0198	7.0944 ± 4.6540	0.394
	1.6	-0.047 ± 1.587	0.0082 ± 0.0153	-0.7758 ± 3.5976	0.767
	1.8	0.473 ± 0.628	0.0071 ± 0.0061	-0.0603 ± 1.4242	0.977
	2	1.867 ± 0.825	0.0176 ± 0.0080	-2.5511 ± 1.8703	0.959
25	1.2	-6.850 ± 2.806	-0.0426 ± 0.0271	9.7423 ± 6.3626	0.575
	1.4	-5.391 ± 1.186	-0.0346 ± 0.0114	8.2070 ± 2.6877	0.652
	1.6	-1.284 ± 1.365	-0.0031 ± 0.0132	1.6073 ± 3.0940	0.726
	1.8	1.335 ± 0.484	0.0152 ± 0.0047	-1.9462 ± 1.0965	0.986
	2	2.230 ± 0.453	0.0217 ± 0.0044	-3.5444 ± 1.0263	0.988
30	1.2	-10.424 ± 1.165	-0.0776 ± 3.6615	17.753 ± 3.662	0.844
	1.4	-6.037 ± 1.296	-0.0414 ± 0.0125	9.784 ± 2.938	0.69
	1.6	-0.272 ± 1.023	0.0052 ± 0.0099	-0.0894 ± 2.3201	0.887

	1.8	0.8704±0.4615	0.0103±0.0045	-0.7091±1.0462	0.989
	2	4.7174±0.7635	0.04349±0.00740	-8.3443±1.7394	0.977
35	1.2	-6.103±2.216	-0.3902±0.02137	9.4237±5.0227	0.435
	1.4	-4.311±1.621	-0.0271±0.0156	6.865±3.6756	0.556
	1.6	-0.499±1.0000	0.0021±0.0096	0.7882±2.2664	0.911
	1.8	1.8302±0.4854	0.0192±0.0047	-2.7572±1.1004	0.988
	2	4.962±1.095	0.0450±0.0106	-8.5601±2.4810	0.961
40	1.2	-8.531±2.370	-0.0618±0.0229	14.4574±5.3720	0.594
	1.4	-3.767±1.273	-0.0238±0.0123	6.3736±2.8847	0.762
	1.6	-0.326±1.063	0.0018±0.0103	1.1504±2.4092	0.932
	1.8	4.123±1.008	0.0390±0.0097	-6.9961±2.2843	0.969
	2.0	7.228±1.525	0.0641±0.0147	-12.584±3.457	0.952

Effect of ionic strength on the distribution constant at infinite dilution of PEG6K

To determine the effect of electrolyte only on the distribution constant at limiting dilution of PEG6K, the values natural logarithm of equilibrium constant of distribution of PEG6K at infinite dilution and fixed ionic strength ($\ln K^{\circ}$) were obtained from the intercepts of the plot of dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG6K}$ on w_{PEG6K} presented Fig. 1 (Table 1). Values of $\ln K^{\circ}$ were obtained at temperatures between 25 and 40°C. The dependence of $\ln K^{\circ}$ on ionic strength at fixed temperature were plotted against ionic strength in Fig. 2 (A – D). Such plot was necessary to determine how ionic strength affect the distribution under very dilute condition of PEG6K at fixed temperature.

Figure 2: Dependence of the natural logarithm of the distribution constant of PEG6K at infinite dilution of PEG6K ($\ln K'^{\circ}$) on ionic strength (NaCl). Temperature conditions: A, 25 °C; B, 30 °C; C, 35 °C and D, 40 °C.

It is clear that at limiting PEG6K dilution, the equilibrium distribution of PEG6K in the aqueous two phase system increases linearly with increasing ionic strength. This provides an incontrovertible proof that increased ionic strength enhance phase separation by promoting attractive interaction between PEG6K molecules. From Eq. (8) since Γ_1 should be equal to 1, under the condition which data in Fig. 2 were reported, the value of Γ_2 which is equal to $\left(\frac{\gamma_{2(\alpha)}}{\gamma_{2(\beta)}}\right)$ should be < 1 and decrease with increasing ionic strength for K'° to increase with increasing ionic strength. In other words, high ionic strength promotes phase separation of PEG6K in the aqueous two phase system by increasing the activity coefficient in the PEG rich β -phase relative to the salt rich α -phase or by reducing the activity coefficient of the salt-rich α -phase relative to the PEG-rich β -phase. This findings suggests that the effective activity coefficient of the solution with respect to salt contribution decreases with increasing salt concentration. This is an indication that the electrolyte interact more intimately with the solvent thus making solvent less available for PEG6K with the result that attractive interaction between PEG6K molecules increases through the enhancement of hydrophobic interaction. This effectively means that decrease activity coefficient of the solution by the addition of the salt electrolyte leads to separation of less hydrophilic PEG6K at the top of the aqueous two phase system.

Equilibrium constant of distribution of PEG70K as a function of its concentration

The dependences of the semi-logarithm of the apparent solid-liquid distribution constant of PEG70K ($\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$) on its concentration (w_{PEG70K}) at ionic strength (0.6 – 1.2 mol. dm⁻³) between 20 and 40°C were presented in Figure 3. The data reported in each panel were at different temperatures. The curve through the experimental data points of Fig. 2 were fitted with Eq. (27) using the fitting parameter reported in Table 2. The correlation of determination of each curve was at least 0.93 (Table 2, column 6). In each panel of Fig. 3, it is obvious that the $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ increases with increasing w_{PEG70K} . It also increases with increasing ionic strength at corresponding w_{PEG70K} . From Table 2, over the entire ionic strength, the value of B_2 is > 0 , indicative of repulsive interaction between PEG70K molecules in solution. However since B_3 is < 0 (suggesting attractive interaction), with increasing concentration of PEG70K, the contribution of attractive term to the activity coefficient dominates the interaction leading to promotion of phase separation. This results in formation of solid PEG70K molecules since dissolution of PEG70K under the conditions of the experiment becomes less favourable with increasing concentration. Values of B_2 were between one and three orders of magnitude greater than the values of B_3 which were < 0 (suggestive of attractive three body interaction). In all cases, $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ increases with w_{PEG70K} and -ve values of B_3 ensures that attractive interaction between PEG70K molecules increases with increasing concentration of PEG70K. It should be noted that as the contribution of attractive contribution to the interaction from the term with B_3 increases with increasing w_{PEG70K} , the equilibrium phase separation increases, however the reduction screening as there are fewer number of ions around per PEG70K molecule results in a positive-sloping concave down curve as w_{PEG70K} increases. The observed increase in phase separation with increasing PEG70K concentration is due to attractive contribution of B_3 coefficient to the PEG70K interaction.

Figure 3: Dependence of the natural logarithm of the apparent phase distribution constant of PEG70K on concentration of PEG70K in phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Symbols: Ionic strength 0.6 mol. dm⁻³ (X and grid curve), 0.8 mol. dm⁻³ (* and short broken line), 1.0 mol. dm⁻³ (■ and long broken line and 1.2 (• and full solid line). Panels (A) 25°C, (B) 30°C, (C) 35°C and (D) 40°C. Curve through experimental data points were fitted using Eq. (27) with the fitting parameters in Table 2. Each experimental data point is the mean of at least three replicate experiment subject to 10% standard error.

Table 2: Fitting parameters of the dependence of the natural logarithm of the apparent solid-liquid distribution constant of PEG70K at ionic strength between 0.6 and 1.2 mol. dm⁻³ according to Eq. (27), between 20°C – 40°C.

Temp. (°C)	I (mol. dm ⁻³)	ln K'' ^o	B ₂ (dm ³ g ⁻¹)	B ₃ x 10 ³ (dm ⁶ g ⁻²)	R ²
20	0.6	-2.620 ± 0.237	0.108 ± 0.017	-1.018 ± 0.277	0.984
	0.8	-3.515 ± 0.457	0.168 ± 0.033	-1.787 ± 0.536	0.967
	1.0	-1.982 ± 0.389	0.084 ± 0.028	-0.600 ± 0.456	0.958
	1.2	-1.916 ± 0.372	0.084 ± 0.027	-5.860 ± 0.436	0.963
25	0.6	-2.451 ± 0.283	0.108 ± 0.021	-1.090 ± 0.332	0.973
	0.8	-2.061 ± 0.279	0.090 ± 0.020	-0.749 ± 0.327	0.974
	1.0	-1.951 ± 0.331	0.090 ± 0.024	-0.735 ± 0.388	0.966
	1.2	-1.580 ± 0.361	0.067 ± 0.026	-0.306 ± 0.423	0.963
30	0.6	-2.323 ± 0.214	0.099 ± 0.016	-0.988 ± 0.251	0.982
	0.8	-2.118 ± 0.261	0.089 ± 0.019	-0.788 ± 0.307	0.975
	1.0	-1.746 ± 0.409	0.078 ± 0.030	-0.652 ± 0.480	0.932
	1.2	-1.442 ± 0.391	0.066 ± 0.028	-0.454 ± 0.458	0.937
35	0.6	-2.309 ± 0.239	0.093 ± 0.017	-0.861 ± 0.280	0.980
	0.8	-2.118 ± 0.262	0.089 ± 0.019	-0.788 ± 0.307	0.975
	1.0	-1.543 ± 0.311	0.059 ± 0.023	-0.319 ± 0.365	0.961
	1.2	-1.293 ± 0.357	0.049 ± 0.026	-0.146 ± 0.419	0.951
40	0.6	-1.991 ± 0.319	0.071 ± 0.023	-0.453 ± 0.374	0.966
	0.8	-1.586 ± 0.402	0.050 ± 0.029	-0.648 ± 0.471	0.951
	1.0	-1.402 ± 0.423	0.046 ± 0.031	0.040 ± 0.496	0.952
	1.2	-0.883 ± 0.506	0.016 ± 0.037	-0.573 ± 0.593	0.939

Effect of ionic strength on the distribution constant at infinite dilution of PEG70K

The values of ln K''^o were obtained at infinite dilution of PEG70K from the plot of dependence of ln K_{D,PEG70K} on w_{PEG70K} at fixed ionic strength such as those presented in Fig. 3. Various values of ln K''^o in Table 2, were plotted against ionic strength under different conditions of temperature between 25 and 40°C in Fig. 4 (A – D). The plot was necessary to determine the effect of ionic strength on the phase distribution of PEG70K under ideal condition with respect to PEG70K. The contribution of PEG70K to the activity coefficient should be equal to 1 under very dilute condition.

Fig. 4: Dependence of the natural logarithm of the distribution constant of infinite dilution of PEG70K ($\ln K^{\infty}$) on ionic strength (NaCl). Temperature condition of the experimental data in each panel are: A, 25 °C; B, 30 °C; C, 35 °C and D, 40 °C.

It is clear that at limiting PEG70K dilution, the equilibrium distribution of PEG6K between the liquid-solid phase system increases linearly with increasing ionic strength according to Eq. (30). This provides an important piece of evidence that increased ionic strength promote repulsive interaction between PEG70K consistent with Eq. (30). In other words, increase in ionic strength promotes phase separation of PEG70K in the two phase system by increasing the activity coefficient of the solution. The effect of this is increased turbidity of the solution due to formation of insoluble PEG70K molecules.

Effect of Temperature on the Phase Distribution PEG6K

To determine how temperature affect the phase distribution of PEG6K at high ionic strength, the dependence of $\ln K_{DPEG6K}$ on w_{PEG6K} at different temperatures were presented in Figure 5. It is seen that though $\ln K_{DPEG6K}$ decreases with w_{PEG6K} at fixed ionic strength (Figs. 5A and 5B), no significant effect of temperature was manifested. This shows that temperature does not significantly affect the phase distribution of PEG6K at high ionic strength.

Fig. 5: Dependence of the natural logarithm of the phase distribution constant on concentration of PEG6K in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at different temperatures and fixed ionic strength (A) 1.8 mol dm^{-3} (B) 2.0 mol dm^{-3} . Symbols: 15°C - X, 20°C - +, 25°C - *, 30°C - Δ , 35°C - \blacksquare , 40°C - O.

Effect of Temperature on the Phase Distribution PEG70K

Effect of phase equilibrium distribution of PEG70K on temperature was determined by plotting the dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ on w_{PEG70K} at different temperature in Fig. 6. Experiment reported in panel A was carried out ionic strength of 0.6 mol. dm^{-3} while that reported in panel B was carried out at 1.2 mol. dm^{-3} ionic strength. It is obvious that within experimental uncertainty, there is no significant temperature effect on the dependence of $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ on w_{PEG70K} . This findings suggest that the effect of temperature on phase separation is entropic rather than enthalpic.

Fig. 6: Dependence of the natural logarithm of the phase distribution constant on concentration of PEG70K in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at different temperatures (A) 0.6 mol dm^{-3} (B) ionic strength 1.2 mol dm^{-3} . Symbols: 15°C - X, 20°C - +, 25°C - *, 30°C - \blacksquare , 40°C - O.

4. Discussion

Comparison of Profiles of PEG6000 and that of PEG70000

Important differences between the aqueous two phase separation containing salt and PEG6K, and two phase separation containing PEG70K and salt are as follows: (i) PEG6K phase separates in the presence adequate salt concentration into two liquids of different densities, whereas, PEG70K phase separates into a solid and a liquid phases. (ii) The weight/volume concentration of PEG6K needed for the onset of phase separation of PEG6K is at least twenty times that which is required for the onset of phase separation in PEG70K at the same ionic strength (iii) Much higher salt ionic strength is required to bring about phase separation in PEG6K than is required for PEG70K despite the relatively lower concentration of PEG70K required for phase separation. It is also

noteworthy that under the conditions of the experiments, at fixed ionic strength, the $\ln K_{D,PEG70K}$ increases with increasing w_{PEG70K} (though not necessarily linearly) whereas, $\ln (K_{D,PEG6K})$ decreases with increasing w_{PEG6K} . This observation suggests that though the two molecules are similar in structure, PEG6K is more sensitive to variation of ionic atmosphere than PEG70K. This difference in behaviour of the two molecules may not be unconnected to the difference in their sizes. It has been previously reported that small molecular weight PEG inhibit cell aggregation whereas high molecular weight PEG promote cell aggregation (Armstrong *et al.*, 2004; Azri *et al.*, 2012; Parray *et al.*, 2020). Both PEG70K and PEG6K phase separation by segregative interaction through enhancement of attractive interaction between the PEG molecules.

5. Conclusion

From the findings of our studies, the two and three body interaction parameters of PEG6k molecules as well as that of PEG70K molecules in solution were determined from the dependence of equilibrium distribution constant of each polymer a function of its concentration under highly non-ideal condition. PEG6K was found to be more amenable to electrostatic interaction than PEG70K. High ionic strength effectively screens the charges on the PEG molecules and other interacting species, minimizing the influence of electrostatic repulsive force on their distribution. The dominant interaction which is responsible for phase separation was attractive. The effectiveness of the salt on each of PEG6K and PEG70K is determined by the relative proportion of electrolyte to the PEG molecules at a fixed temperature. Though there are evidences to show that increased temperature favour aqueous two phase separation of PEG6K as well as phase separation involving PEG70K, the findings of this experiment demonstrates that the phase separation processes of both PEG types is essentially an entropically driven process. From the findings of the experiment, salt enhance phase separation of PEG6K in solution by lowering the activity coefficient of the salt rich phase and increasing the activity coefficient of the PEG-rich phase, with the result that the effective activity coefficient is < 1 and reduces with increasing salt concentration in the salt-rich phase. This finding is consistent with earlier data reported. Snyder *et al.*, 1992). On the other hand, increased concentration of salt increases phase distribution constant of PEG70K by increasing the activity coefficient of its solution.

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